

Transmission of rice tungro by green leafhopper (GLH) on successive days

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We studied transmission of tungro by viruliferous GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) to 25 rice varieties and cultures on successive days of inoculation feeding, and insect survival in the greenhouse.

Fifth-instar nymphs were allowed to feed on tungro-infected plants for 4 d for virus acquisition. One viruliferous insect was released in a test tube containing one 10-d-old rice seedling for inoculation (100 seedlings per variety). Seedlings were removed after 24 h (taking care to retain the live insect inside the test tube) and transplanted in pots. A fresh seedling of the same variety and age was immediately placed in the test tube for the viruliferous GLH to transmit tungro on successive days. This procedure was repeated at 24-h intervals until the death of all insects.

Infected seedlings were counted 21 d after transplanting (see table).

For testing insect longevity, third-instar GLH nymphs 9-11 d old were allowed to feed on tungro-infected TN1 plants for 4 d. Each insect was released into a test tube containing one 10-d-old seedling. For each variety, 20 seedlings and 20 viruliferous insects were used. Surviving insects were counted at 24-h intervals and seedlings replaced, until the death of all insects.

Viruliferous insects could transmit tungro only on the first and second days to 7 varieties (see table). They transmitted tungro up to 5 d on ADT36 and TN1. Transmission to the rest of the varieties ceased after 3 or 4 d.

Insect longevity was shortest (12-14 d) on IR72 and IR33043-46-1-3. The insect survived for more than 20 d on most of the popular varieties, with a maximum of more than 41 d on TN1.

GLH could transmit tungro up to only 2 d and survive the shortest time (12-18 d) on IR72, IR50, IR33043-46-1-3, TNAU831521, IR52431-60-1-2-1, IR39657-91-3-2-3, and TNAULFR842718. ■

Resistance of breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis* to brown planthopper (BPH)

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We evaluated 195 breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis* for resistance to the Indian population of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal). PTB33 and TN1 served as the resistant and susceptible checks.

Seeds of each test line were sown in 12-cm rows in 60- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with five replications.

Seedlings were thinned to 30/row 7 d after sowing and infested with about 8 second-instar BPH nymphs per seedling. When 90% of TN1 seedlings were dead, all breeding lines were rated for plant damage.

Of the breeding lines evaluated, 54 exhibited high levels of resistance (score 1) to the Indian population of BPH:

Transmission of tungro to rice plants on successive days (1-5). Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Mean life span ^a (d)	Tungro transmission (%) on successive feeding days				
		1	2	3	4	5
IR72	12.1 a	20	10	0	0	0
IR33043-46-1-3	12.6 ab	20	10	0	0	0
IR50404-57-2-2-3	15.8 c	30	20	20	0	0
IR52431-60-1-2-1	15.9 c	20	20	0	0	0
IR34686-56-2-2-2	16.6 c	30	20	20	0	0
CRM25	16.8 c	30	10	10	0	0
TNAULFR842718	18.0 d	30	30	0	0	0
AS33773	21.2 ef	30	20	20	0	0
IR32429-148-13-3	22.0 efg	20	20	10	0	0
IR37865-29-3-13	20.9 c	30	30	10	0	0
IR39357-91-3-2-3	16.0 c	20	10	0	0	0
TNAU831520	22.3 fg	30	30	20	0	0
TNAU831521	13.4 b	20	10	0	0	0
IR50	18.8 d	20	10	0	0	0
IR64	13.8 h	30	20	10	0	0
ASD17	22.0 efg	30	30	20	0	0
MDU3	31.6 i	50	40	20	0	0
Ponni	23.1 g	40	20	20	0	0
White Ponni	25.8 h	50	30	30	0	0
IR20	35.1 j	70	50	50	30	0
CO 37	35.0 j	80	60	40	20	0
CO 43	35.1 j	70	70	40	10	0
ADT36	38.1 l	80	70	50	30	20
ADT38	36.3 k	60	50	30	30	0
TN1	41.4 m	100	70	70	04	30

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

IR54742-1-18-12-11-2	IR54745-1-20-17-8-3
IR54742-23-19-16-10-3	IR54742-11-8-7-3-3
IR54742-1-20-10-11-1	IR54745-2-21-12-17-2
IR54742-23-19-16-12-1	IR54742-11-10-13-21-1
IR54742-1-20-10-11-2	IR54745-2-23-19-8-1
IR54742-23-19-16-12-2	IR54742-11-15-3-7-2
IR54742-1-20-10-11-3	IR54745-2-34-3-10-3
IR54742-25-1-23-7-1	IR54742-13-29-12-9-1
IR54742-4-7-9-7-1	IR54745-2-45-3-24-3
IR54742-25-1-23-7-3	IR54742-13-29-12-9-2
IR54742-5-36-4-17-2	IR54751-2-41-10-5-1
IR54742-31-9-26-15-3	IR54742-18-3-8-10-3
IR54742-5-36-4-17-3	IR54751-2-41-10-5-2
IR54742-31-16-25-22-3	IR54742-18-17-20-15-1
IR54742-6-1-14-15-1	IR54751-2-41-10-5-3
IR54742-31-21-20-10-2	IR54742-18-17-20-15-3
IR54742-6-1-14-15-2	IR54751-4-6-7-21-2
IR54742-33-9-14-26-2	IR54742-22-19-3-7-2
IR54742-6-1-14-15-3	IR54751-4-6-7-21-3
IR54742-33-9-14-26-3	IR54742-22-19-3-7-3
IR54742-6-20-3-9-1	IR54751-4-22-10-17-2
IR54742-33-9-14-26-4	IR54742-22-19-3-15-3
IR54742-11-2-8-2-1	IR54751-4-25-4-17-1
IR54745-2-2-25-26-3	IR54742-23-11-19-6-3
IR54742-11-2-8-2-2	IR54752-50-19-19-1
IR54745-2-10-17-8-1	IR54742-23-19-16-10-2
IR54742-11-8-7-3-2	IR54742-50-19-19-3